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Awareness and Knowledge of the Magna Carta for Teachers Among Public School Teachers

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Introduction

"Teachers play a vital role in shaping humanity, serving as the foundation of education and civilization. The progress of any nation relies on their dedicated involvement."- John Adams

The teacher serves as a representative of society, instilling moral principles in students. In the development of a nation, significant emphasis must be placed on both education and moral values, with the teacher being uniquely positioned to contribute to this process. Without teachers, both knowledge and morality would face decline.

The role of a teacher is many-sided, including academic, pedagogical, and social responsibilities. Academically, teachers are responsible for instruction, counseling, and supervision. Pedagogically, they take on tasks related to instruction, evaluation, and facilitating the learning process. As facilitators of learning, teachers motivate students, maintain discipline within the classroom and school, and create an environment conducive to learning.

The social responsibilities of teachers extend beyond the classroom. They help students adapt to societal norms and expectations, acting as guides in their socialization. Additionally, teachers often fulfill other roles, such as serving as role models, mentors, confidants, and sometimes even parental figures, providing emotional support and care to their students (Sethi, 2009).

The primary responsibility of a teacher is to educate students, providing instruction that equips them for higher education and future employment (Rachel Morgan). Teachers are expected to not only convey subject knowledge but also adapt their teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of their students. Effective teaching goes beyond the mere transmission of information; it involves engaging students in a way that fosters understanding and retention.

Teachers play a pivotal role in shaping a nation's future, and as such, governments prioritize improving their working conditions. Safeguarding that teachers are well-supported helps retain dedicated educators who are crucial for the delivery of quality education. Various laws and provisions have been enacted to ensure that teachers are provided with a standard of living that reflects their importance to society.

Beyond their educational duties, teachers often contribute to civic activities that benefit the community and the nation. For instance, teachers frequently serve as members of

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the Board of Election Inspectors during elections and assist the National Statistics Office in gathering household data. These non-teaching responsibilities, while significant, are often performed outside of official working hours without adequate compensation.

In the Department of Education (DepEd), many teachers express concerns about excessive non-instructional duties that burden them, as well-known in the Magna Carta for Teachers. Despite these extra responsibilities, the compensation they receive does not always reflect the effort and time they invest in their work. This discrepancy between workload and salary has been a recurring issue, affecting teachers' well-being and job satisfaction.

In this situation, Republic Act No. 4670, or the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers, aims to enhance the social and economic status of teachers by improving their living and working conditions, employment terms, and career prospects. This Act seeks to attract and retain qualified educators, recognizing that quality education and national economic development depend on their capabilities. The researcher aims to examine the implementation of this law, teachers' awareness of its provisions, and their satisfaction with the benefits it offers. Understanding these factors is essential for assessing the law's effectiveness in improving the teaching profession and contributing to national progress through education

Background of the Study

In every country, governments strive to ensure the best conditions for their teachers to promote retention and enable them to effectively fulfill their duties in providing quality education for learners. Various laws and policies have been enacted to ensure that teachers are provided with a dignified and stable standard of living. In the Philippines, teachers are frequently called upon to take on additional civic responsibilities that benefit both the community and the nation. Among the most notable of these duties are their roles as members of the Board of Election Inspectors during election periods and their assistance to the National Statistics Office in conducting household data collection across the country. Unfortunately, these non-teaching tasks, often performed beyond official working hours, are not adequately compensated. The Philippines is no exception to this situation, where teachers regularly engage in non-teaching activities that serve the broader public. Despite these contributions, the lack of fair compensation for extra tasks remains a pressing concern. In this context, the researcher seeks to examine the working conditions of teachers, particularly in relation to the implementation of the Magna Carta for Teachers, to assess whether the law is being upheld and if it sufficiently addresses the needs of educators.

Synthesis. Teachers in the Philippines face stress due to limited understanding of their rights under the Magna Carta for Teachers. Many lack proper training and resources, making it difficult to manage workloads and career growth. Inconsistent support from school leaders adds to this strain. To address these issues, better training and advocacy are needed to empower teachers and create a more supportive work environment.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the following theories, concepts, and principles: Johnson Motivation Theory, Victor Vroom's Theory, Adam's Equity Theory, Job Enrichment Theory, and Maslow's Hierarchy Theory.

Everyone works in expectation of some rewards and benefits. Employee benefits are very important as part of an employee's financial security. Benefits have the ability to attract

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and retain employees and also may perceive dissatisfaction, which results in job demotivation, a higher level of absenteeism, a lower level of performance, and a higher turnover rate.

Motivation Theory

Johnson (1986) states that there are three theories of motivation and productivity that teacher motivation is based on:

Expectancy Theory by Victor Vroom, 1964

An individual will struggle for work if there is an expected reward, such as a bonus. It states that when an employee is completing a task, they are influenced by their view on: (1) the probability of completing the task and (2) the probable outcome or consequence of completing the task.

Expectancy Theory suggests that individuals choose actions based on their belief that those actions will lead to rewards or minimize pain. The ultimate goal itself is less important than the personal impact of achieving that goal. According to Vroom's Expectancy Theory, several factors influence an individual's perception, including:

- Expectancy: does the individual believe that they can achieve the task?
- Valence: does the individual believe that completing the task will benefit them or cause detriment?
- Instrumentality: what is the probability of completing the task leading to an outcome desired by the individual?

Equity Theory by Adams

Adams (1965) posits that individuals are motivated to seek social equity in the rewards for their performance. When treated unfairly, employees tend to feel demotivated, whereas fair treatment enhances motivation. Adams' Equity Theory emphasizes the need for a balance between an employee's inputs (such as effort and skills) and outputs (like salary and recognition). Achieving this balance fosters a strong, productive relationship, resulting in satisfied and motivated employees.

Proposition of Equity theory:

1. Outcome maximization. Individuals strive to maximize their outcomes, defined as rewards minus costs.
2. Collective Reward Systems. Groups can enhance collective rewards by establishing systems for fairly distributing rewards and costs among members. These equity systems will develop within groups, where members encourage adherence to them. To promote equitable behavior, groups must make it more beneficial for members to act fairly than unfairly, rewarding equitable behavior and penalizing inequitable actions.
3. Distress in Inequitable Relationships. When individuals find themselves in inequitable relationships, they experience distress. The level of distress increases with the degree of inequality, affecting both parties involved. Those who receive too much may feel guilt or shame, while those who receive too little may feel anger or humiliation.
4. Restoring Equity. Individuals who perceive inequity in a relationship seek to alleviate their distress by restoring equity. The greater the perceived inequity, the more distress individuals feel and the more they strive to achieve equity (Walster, Traupmann, and Walster, 1978).

Maslow's Hierarchy Theory

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Maslow's hierarchy theory is a well-known motivation framework. Employee benefit programs can be categorized into four types of welfare demands: physical, security, social, and self-actualization. Lower-level demands must be satisfied before higher-level demands can be addressed.

1. **Physiological Needs.** These are the most fundamental needs essential for survival, including water, air, food, and sleep. Maslow emphasized that all other needs become secondary until these physiological needs are satisfied.
2. **Security Needs.** These encompass the need for safety and security, including steady employment, healthcare, safe neighborhoods, and shelter. While important for survival, they are less urgent than physiological needs.
3. **Social Needs.** These involve the need for belonging, love, and affection. Relationships, friendships, and community involvement help fulfill the desire for companionship and acceptance, making these needs less basic than physiological and security needs.
4. **Esteem Needs.** Once the first three needs are met, esteem needs gain importance. They involve self-esteem, personal worth, social recognition, and a sense of accomplishment.
5. **Self-actualizing Needs.** This is the highest level in Maslow's hierarchy, where individuals seek personal growth and self-awareness, focusing on fulfilling their potential rather than the opinions of others.

Implementation of the Republic Act
4670

(The Magna Carta for Public School
Teachers)

Figure 1. Research Paradigm.

Figure 1. shows the research paradigm of the study. The study will investigate the implementation of the Magna Carta for public school teachers. First, the study will involve finding out the extent of awareness and knowledge of the Magna Carta by the administrators and teachers. It will involve the extent of availment of the teachers on their rights as provided for in the law. Finally, the teacher's level of availment will be determined as well as the level of satisfaction in terms of the salient provisions, actual teaching condition, and career prospect.

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Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the implementation of the Teachers Welfare Provision of the Magna Carta for Teachers. *Specifically, the study will seek to answer the following questions:*

1. To what extent are the principals and teachers aware and knowledgeable of the provisions of the Magna Carta for Teachers?;
2. To what extent have teachers benefited from the provisions of the Magna Carta?;
3. What are the career opportunities available for teachers?;
4. What is the level of satisfaction of the teachers with the implementation of the Magna Carta? and
5. Is there a significant connection between teachers' knowledge, availment, and satisfaction with the Magna Carta?.

Hypotheses:

- Ho1: There is a significant relationship among knowledge and awareness, availment, and level of satisfaction of the teachers in the Magna Carta for teachers.
- Ho2: There is a significant relationship between the implementation of R.A. 4670 or the provision for the Magna Carta for the Public School Teacher and the teachers actual teaching condition.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will help the Department of Education family, especially those in the Division of Lanao del Norte.

Department of Education- Division of Lanao del Norte. The study provides information on the extent of implementation of the Magna Carta for teachers in the public elementary and secondary schools. This also will enable the Division of Lanao del Norte to take initiatives to implement the provisions.

Public School Teachers, this study will help them be aware of the rights and privileges intended for them.

Government officials. The results of this study will hopefully enlighten the government officials to have some amendments to Republic Act 7460, also known as the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers, in order to be attuned to the present times.

Future researchers. This study was benefited for having an advance insight to the Awareness and Knowledge of the Magna Carta for Teachers Among Public School Teachers.

Scope and Delimitation of Study

The study will be limited only to the principals and teachers in Lanao del Norte who have been employed at DepEd for at least 3 years. They may be employed either at the elementary or secondary level in the Division of Lanao del Norte. Furthermore, this study will be limited only to the provisions that relate to teachers welfare.

Definition of terms

Awareness. The state or condition of being aware; having knowledge; consciousness.

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Availment. Profit; advantage.

Magna Carta for Public School Teachers. Magna Carta for public school teachers serves as the guide to “utter” protection and freedom, away from threats and terminations from the concerned authorities.

Need. Require something because it is essential or very important.

Public School Teacher. A school that is maintained at public expense for the education of the children of a community or district and that constitutes a part of a system of free public education commonly including primary and secondary schools.

Satisfaction. The state of being satisfied; contentment.

Theoretical Framework

In recent days, Filipino teachers clamor and some of the senators, congressmen, and party list questioned the implementation of Republic Act 4670, commonly known as the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers. The number of House bills has been discussed yet, and until this very moment it has not been realized.

The provision has not been fully implemented since there is no alignment of Republic Act 4670 to the actual teachers teaching conditions. The scenario may lead the teachers to get involved in some activities just to earn money to feed their daily needs. And for those who got a chance to teach abroad, they will be going to leave the Department of Education to have greener pasture. They prefer to leave their families since they will be paid more than ten (10) times the basic salary in the DepEd.

Research Paradigm.

This study explores the implementation of the Magna Carta for public school teachers, using qualitative methods to assess its effectiveness and impact on teachers' rights and working conditions.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to assess the extent of principals' and teachers' knowledge and awareness of the provisions of the Magna Carta for Teachers, the level of availment of these provisions by teachers, their career prospects, and their satisfaction with the implementation of the law. Furthermore, it seeks to determine if there is a significant relationship between teachers' knowledge, availment, and satisfaction with the Magna Carta.

Significance of the Study

The study benefits:

Department of Education- Division of Lanao del Norte. Enable the Department of Education (DepEd) to take initiatives to implement the provisions.

Public School Teachers. To be aware of the rights and privileges intended for them.

Government officials. Enlighten on the amendments to Republic Act 7460, also known as Magna Carta for Public School Teachers, in order to be attuned to the present times.

Future researchers. This study used as references for the future researcher that serves as guide, bases in conducting similar problem.

Definition of Terms

Awareness. The state or condition of being aware; having knowledge; consciousness.

Availment. This refers to taking advantage of the rights and privileges as cited in the Magna Carta for Teachers.

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Magna Carta for Public School Teachers. The law aims to promote and improve the social and economic status of public school teachers, their living and working conditions, their terms of employment, and their career prospects.

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive correlational type of research will be utilized in this study. It will evaluate the implementation of R.A. 4670, commonly known as Magna Carta for Public School Teachers. It will also investigate to what extent the teachers are aware and knowledgeable of this law. Furthermore, it will determine the availability and level of satisfaction of the teachers with the implementation of Magna Carta.

Research Locale and Respondents

The study was conducted during the 2nd semester of the school year 2023-2024 at the public elementary and secondary schools in the Division of Lanao del Norte. The participants will be the principals and teachers who have been in the service for at least three (3) years.

Research Instruments

Four (4) sets of questionnaires will be used to determine the extent of knowledge and awareness of teachers and principals of the Magna Carta. The researcher prepared types of checklists. The first set will be on the level of awareness, the second will be the level of knowledge, the third will be on the availment of the Magna Carta, and the fourth will be on the level of satisfaction with the salient provisions, teacher actual teaching condition, and career prospect.

Data Gathering Procedure

The number of participants will be determined by using the Slovin Formula. The principals and teachers will be selected by drawing lots. However, to determine the knowledge and awareness of the principals and teachers, a checklist will be answered. Likewise, for principals and teachers, a checklist will be used to determine the extent of implementation and working conditions of the teachers.

Statistical Treatment

To analyze the data, the researcher will be using the mean and percentage. To determine whether significant differences exist between the implementation of the R.A. 4670 or the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers and the actual teachers teaching conditions, the regression analysis will be used in the study.

References

The study references a wide range of sources, including academic articles, journals, and research papers on Awareness and Knowledge of the Magna Carta for Teachers Among Public School Teachers.

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